

Rainwater Harvesting and Reuse Systems in Bangalore: A Response to the Water Scarcity

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Abstract

Bangalore faces acute water scarcity due to rapid urbanization, declining groundwater levels, and overreliance on the Cauvery River, with a daily shortfall of approximately 500 million liters. Rainwater harvesting (RWH) offers a decentralized, sustainable approach to enhance urban water resilience. This study systematically reviews the adoption, typologies, effectiveness, and policy frameworks of RWH systems in Bangalore using secondary data from government reports, academic literature, NGOs, and case studies. Findings show that rooftop storage and groundwater recharge dominate RWH practices, collectively harvesting around 53 MLD, yet covering only a fraction of citywide demand. Policy interventions, notably the 2009 BWSSB RWH mandate and its 2021 expansion, alongside technical support from KSCST and BBMP initiatives, have facilitated adoption. Barriers remain, including financial costs, technical challenges, and limited awareness, with uptake largely compliance-driven. Despite these constraints, RWH contributes significantly to groundwater recharge, reduces reliance on piped water, and mitigates urban water stress. Strengthening community engagement, technical standards, and incentives is critical for scaling RWH. These insights inform sustainable urban water management and policy development in rapidly growing Indian cities.

Keywords: Water scarcity, Rainwater harvesting, Groundwater recharge, Urban water management, Bangalore, Sustainable development, Water policy, Community participation, Climate change, Urbanization

1. Introduction:

Water scarcity is a pressing challenge in rapidly urbanizing regions, particularly in developing economies. Bangalore, a major technological and economic hub of India, is increasingly facing water stress due to rapid population growth, erratic rainfall patterns, and over-extraction of groundwater (S. Vishwanath, 2015). Bengaluru was once called the 'City of Lakes', with over 1,000 lakes across the city. But today, things have changed - the city is now facing serious water scarcity, a big shift from its water-rich past (B.PAC, 2024)

The city's water supply mainly comes from two sources: the Cauvery River, which provides 51%, and groundwater, which makes up the remaining 49%. The distribution of Cauvery water is managed by the Bangalore Water Supply and Sewerage Board (BWSSB), whereas groundwater supply is handled by private organizations (Kulranjan et al., 2023). According to a report from WELL LABS, 72% of Bangalore's water is used for domestic activities such as cooking, drinking, bathing, and. Commercial and industrial activities use about 24%, including manufacturing, cooling, and services. Construction accounts for 3% of water usage, mainly for concrete mixing and curing, while 1% goes toward watering green spaces such as parks, gardens, and urban forests (Kulranjan et al., 2023).

WELL LABS estimates that Bangalore generates approximately 1,940 million liters of wastewater daily, about the same as the volume of eight Olympic-sized swimming pools. Of this amount, 64% is treated at Central Sewage Treatment Plants, and 13% at Decentralized Treatment Plants. However, around 23% remains untreated and is discharged into rivers and lakes, worsening water pollution. Alarmingly, only 5% of the treated water is reused, with this small portion being supplied to areas within the city and to nearby districts such as Bangalore Rural, Kolar, and Chikballapur (Kulranjan et al., 2023).

Bangalore's water crisis has wide-ranging implications, impacting both its population and industrial sector. The scarcity of water hampers everyday life by limiting access to safe drinking water and adequate sanitation. Industrial operations also suffer, resulting in decreased productivity and hindering economic development. According to (Mint, 2024) reports, the city is increasingly dependent on groundwater; however, more than 6,900 of its 14,000 borewells have run dry due to declining groundwater levels. Bangalore currently requires approximately 2,600 million litres of water per day (MLD) to meet both domestic and industrial needs. Out of this

demand, 1,450 MLD is sourced from the Cauvery River at an added financial cost, while 650 MLD comes from the city's borewells. Despite these efforts, there remains a shortfall of 500 MLD in 2024 (The Hindu, 2024).

Bangalore's ongoing water crisis is largely fueled by the long-standing and often contentious dispute over the Cauvery River, a crucial water source shared by both Karnataka and Tamil Nadu. This inter-state conflict, intensified by competing demands from growing populations and agricultural sectors, has escalated into a geopolitical impasse (Bosu, 1995).

Adding to these challenges is the impact of climate change, which has introduced instability into the regional water cycle. Rainfall patterns have become increasingly erratic, marked by unseasonal rains and extended dry spells, undermining established water management systems and exacerbating shortages in the city (Thokchom, 2020). The once-reliable monsoon season, critical for replenishing water sources, is now unpredictable, complicating already strained efforts to manage water supply effectively.

Bangalore's explosive urban growth further complicates this situation. Over the past five decades (1973–2023), Bangalore's urbanized area grew from 8% to 93.3%, showing a dramatic and sustained urban expansion (Mehta & Saroha, 2024). The shift from a quiet town to a major tech hub has put immense pressure on natural resources, especially water. Rapid urbanization has led to excessive groundwater extraction, contamination of surface water bodies, and encroachment upon vital catchment areas (Raju et al., 2018). These human-driven changes have not only drained the city's water reserves but have also weakened its capacity to manage them in a sustainable way.

Moreover, Bangalore's overdependence on rapidly declining groundwater and the lack of effective rainwater harvesting systems continue to worsen the crisis. The problem is further intensified by inefficiencies in the city's water distribution system, with 40%–50% of water reportedly lost due to leaks and unauthorized usage (Satpathy & Jha, 2022).

Figure 1. A woman carries water pots after collecting water from a municipal tanker during Bangalore's ongoing water crisis. Source: Getty Image

Motivation:

The motivation for this study arises from the urgent need to address the escalating water scarcity crisis in Bangalore. We rely completely on rivers, lakes, and groundwater to meet our water needs. However, all of these sources are ultimately sustained by rainfall. Water is an essential part of our lives, as it is a valuable natural resource. Rainwater harvesting (RWH) presents a viable, decentralized solution to reduce reliance on external sources and improve water resilience in the region.

This study aligns with SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation) by addressing urban water security. Findings will inform policy reforms and community engagement strategies, critical for emerging economies facing similar challenges. RWH has numerous benefits, including groundwater recharge, reduced dependence on piped water supply, and mitigation of urban flooding.

Despite these advantages, challenges persist, including poor technical execution, lack of awareness, and ineffective maintenance of RWH systems. This study aims to bridge these knowledge gaps by identifying key drivers and barriers to RWH adoption in Bangalore.

2. Aim and Objectives

This research investigates the existing rainwater conservation methods employed across different sectors (households, apartments, public spaces, and industrial) in Bangalore, assessing their effectiveness in mitigating water scarcity. The study will also explore policy frameworks, technological applications, and community engagement in RWH. These findings will be crucial for strengthening water management strategies and formulating policy recommendations that promote the widespread adoption of RWH, contributing to sustainable urban development

Key Objectives:

1. Assess the current implementation and performance of RWH systems in Bangalore.
2. Explore the role of government policies and community-led initiatives in promoting RWH.
3. Recommend strategies for scaling up RWH across urban Bangalore.

3. Methodology:

This study primarily involved the collection, analysis, and synthesis of secondary data to evaluate rainwater harvesting (RWH) systems in Bangalore. The methodology integrates a systematic literature review with case study analysis to assess current adoption, policy frameworks, and the effectiveness of RWH in improving urban water resilience.

Materials

The research is based on an in-depth examination of existing literature, policy documents, and empirical case studies focusing on rainwater harvesting initiatives in Bangalore

Data Sources

A variety of credible secondary sources were used for this study, including:

- Academic Journals: Peer-reviewed articles on rainwater harvesting and water conservation, with a specific focus on Bangalore.

- **Government Reports:** Documents from the Bangalore Water Supply and Sewerage Board (BWSSB), and Karnataka State Council for Science and Technology (KSCST) detailing water usage patterns, regulatory frameworks, and RWH guidelines.
- **NGO Publications:** Reports and project evaluations by organizations like WELL LABS and Rainwater Club,
- **Case Studies:** Detailed studies of local initiatives, including the Kothanur Village pilot and the RWH Theme Park in Jayanagar, Bangalore.
- **News Articles and Media Reports:** Coverage from regional newspapers and environmental platforms discussing public responses, policy updates, and challenges in RWH adoption.

3.1.2. Data Collection Methods

Literature Review

A structured and comprehensive literature review was conducted. The steps included:

- **Keyword Searches:** Databases such as Google Scholar, Scopus, and JSTOR were queried using keywords like “Bangalore rainwater harvesting,” “urban water scarcity,” “groundwater recharge,” and “BWSSB regulations.”
- **Selection Criteria:** Studies were included based on relevance, credibility, and recency (preferably published within the last 20 years), with a primary focus on Bengaluru.

Data Extraction

The selected sources were reviewed, and the following types of information were extracted:

- **Types of RWH Systems:** Descriptions of technologies and practices such as rooftop harvesting, recharge wells, and infiltration trenches.
- **Performance Metrics:** Water savings, groundwater level improvement, and cost-effectiveness of various RWH models.
- **Regulatory Frameworks:** Insights into mandates and policies, including the BWSSB RWH Regulation (2009).

- **Implementation Challenges:** Technical, institutional, financial, and community-related barriers to widespread adoption.
- **Public Participation:** Role of awareness, incentives, and grassroots engagement in successful RWH initiatives.

3.1.3. Data Analysis

The extracted data were analyzed through:

- **Thematic Analysis:** Identifying recurring themes such as policy effectiveness, system performance, implementation barriers, and community engagement.

3.1.4. Synthesis of Findings

The final step involved synthesizing the findings to derive a comprehensive understanding of the rainwater harvesting landscape in Bengaluru. This included:

- Evaluating the scalability of successful models
- Developing actionable recommendations for improving RWH adoption across the city

The synthesized insights aim to support future policy formulation, stakeholder engagement, and technical interventions that promote sustainable and decentralized urban water management in Bengaluru.

4. Results

4.1 Emergence and Typologies of Rainwater Harvesting (RWH) in Bangalore

The adoption of rainwater harvesting (RWH) in Bengaluru accelerated following the 2009 BWSSB Amendment Act, which mandated RWH for plots $\geq 2,400$ sq. ft and new constructions above 1,200 sq. ft (BWSSB, 2021). This regulation marked a turning point in urban water governance, compelling thousands of households, institutions, and commercial establishments to adopt harvesting structures. In 2021, the scope was widened to include older 60×40 ft plots, further intensifying adoption (Vivek Kumar Sah, 2024).

Bengaluru's unique hydrogeology dominated by fractured hard-rock aquifers, has shaped the typologies of RWH adopted. Direct rooftop collection for storage has been implemented but

remains limited due to high capital costs, maintenance needs, and treatment requirements. Instead, the dominant practice is recharge-oriented harvesting, whereby rooftop or surface runoff is directed into recharge pits, infiltration trenches, or percolation wells to augment groundwater (Kulranjan et al., 2023).

The city also hosts the Rainwater Harvesting Theme Park at Jayanagar, developed by BWSSB and KSCST, which showcases 27 operational RWH models. This park has become an essential hub for citizen training, technical demonstrations, and professional awareness (BWSSB, 2021).

4.1.1 Typologies of RWH in Practice

1. Rooftop harvesting with storage: Typically involves Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) downpipes, first-flush diverters, and filtration units feeding sumps or tanks. Stored water is mostly used for non-potable purposes such as gardening, flushing, and cleaning. In limited cases, treated rooftop runoff has been extended to potable uses (Citizen Matters, 2025).
2. Groundwater recharge systems:
 - Recharge pits and percolation wells: Most common, using RCC rings or infiltration trenches with silt traps.
 - Borewell-linked recharge: Some households divert rooftop water directly into borewells or open wells, though BWSSB explicitly warns against unfiltered direct recharge due to contamination risks (BWSSB, 2021).
3. Community-scale recharge:
 - Tree-based percolation pits in parks and along roads.
 - Bruhat Bengaluru Mahanagara Palike (BBMP) set to install new 1,500 rainwater recharge wells across 306 parks(SANDRP, 2025).

Figure: Ground water recharge pit

Figure: Rooftop RWH

Figure: Residents from multiple apartments and private houses have installed recharge wells.

4.2 Effectiveness of RWH in Reducing Water Demand and Recharging Groundwater

Survey-based evidence highlights that rooftop harvesting and recharge-oriented systems are both significant contributors to Bengaluru's water resilience. Rooftop catchments covering 24 km² harvest about 18 MLD annually (17 MLD in dry months and 20 MLD in wet months), while urban lakes add an additional 35 MLD through recharge (Kulranjan et al., 2023).

Public perception aligns with this effectiveness: respondents in a recent Bengaluru survey reported that RWH is most valued for preventing future water crises and improving groundwater levels, while potable uses remain least preferred due to quality concerns (Ambika & Shankar, 2023). Citizens also emphasized its role in reducing bills, serving domestic purposes, and preventing flooding.

Nonetheless, technical challenges such as poor filtration, misaligned recharge pits, and inadequate maintenance continue to limit performance (Citizen Matters, 2025). Recent hydrogeological modeling confirms that artificial recharge, including RWH, contributes

significantly to Bengaluru's aquifer balance ((Tomer et al., 2021)). However, without strict safeguards, recharge into borewells may risk contamination, underscoring the need for proper siting and filtration standards (BWSSB, 2021).

4.3 Policy Framework and Institutional Interventions

The BWSSB remains the central regulatory body, enforcing compliance, issuing technical guidelines, and operating the Jayanagar RWH Park. Enforcement has intensified: in January 2025 alone, penalties collected for non-compliance exceeded ₹2.7 crore, and surcharge slabs for domestic and commercial users were raised to 100–200% (The Times of India, 2025).

The Karnataka State Council for Science and Technology (KSCST) supports technical training, while the BBMP integrates recharge wells into public parks. By October 2025, BBMP aims to complete 4,239 recharge wells across 510 parks, contributing an estimated 543 ML annually (Garima & Sridhar, 2025). The Bangalore Water Supply and Sewerage Board (BWSSB) has introduced a community rainwater harvesting project to channel runoff into urban lakes, thereby supporting groundwater recharge and addressing water scarcity in the city (The New Indian Express, 2024)

4.4 Community Participation and Drivers of Adoption

RWH adoption in Bengaluru is still primarily compliance-driven, but awareness and willingness to adopt are steadily improving. By 2023, 1.93 lakh properties were compliant, rising to 2.1 lakh by early 2025, though about 42,000 eligible properties remained non-compliant (The Times of India, 2025; Puran Choudhary, 2023)).

Survey data reinforce this trend: 61% of homeowners reported installing RWH systems, compared to only 30% of tenants. Awareness is relatively high - 74.8% of respondents knew about BWSSB mandate, but a quarter of citizens remain uninformed (Ambika & Shankar, 2023). Education and employment background also influence adoption, though even highly educated groups cited cost and maintenance burdens as reasons for hesitation.

Encouragingly, 28% of non-adopters expressed willingness to install RWH if they received financial or technical support (Citizen Matters, 2025). This highlights the importance of coupling

mandates with incentives, outreach, and hands-on guidance to convert awareness into voluntary adoption.

4.5 Technical and Economic Considerations

Recent estimates place the cost of rooftop direct-use systems at ₹20,000–50,000, while a recharge well of 3 ft × 20 ft depth costs ₹50,000–70,000 (Citizen Matters, 2025). These costs are significantly higher than the ~₹15,000 baseline reported in 2013 (Umamani & Manasi, 2013), reflecting inflation and deeper recharge requirements.

Design quality remains uneven. BWSSB recommends mandatory first-flush diverters, filtration before recharge, safe distance from soak pits, and desilting every five years (BWSSB, 2021). Maintenance issues, especially clogged filters, are still frequently reported (Citizen Matters, 2025).

4.6 Current Scope and Scenarios

Despite a 15-year regulatory regime, adoption remains incomplete and fragmented. Estimates suggest that 18 MLD is harvested annually from rooftops, with an additional 35 MLD via lakes together covering only a fraction of the city's 2,632 MLD demand (Kulranjan et al., 2023).

As of 2025, compliance among mandated properties is 84%, reflecting progress but also underscoring gaps in enforcement and citizen engagement (Times of India, 2025). The potential exists to double harvested volumes if direct-use systems are scaled in apartments, while BBMP's park and lake initiatives signal a shift toward community-scale recharge.

5. Discussion/ Main Takeaways

The findings reaffirm the strategic role of RWH in alleviating Bengaluru's water stress, especially amid increasing reliance on unsustainable groundwater extraction and dwindling Cauvery River supplies.

Adoption and typologies: Bengaluru demonstrates two dominant systems: rooftop harvesting for storage (mostly for non-potable uses such as gardening and toilet flushing) and groundwater recharge systems. Together, these reduce dependence on tankers and 6000 wells of water, although recharge remains the more widely adopted practice.

Effectiveness: Survey data confirm positive impacts on groundwater levels, though effectiveness varies by system design, filtration quality, and aquifer alignment. Poorly designed pits and inadequate pre-filtration can lead to reduced recharge efficiency and water quality risks.

Policy and institutional support: BWSSB's 2009 mandate, later expanded in 2021, was pivotal in scaling adoption. KSCST and BBMP contributed through technical training, demonstration projects, and integration of recharge pits in public parks. Nonetheless, enforcement and compliance remain uneven.

Barriers: Lack of awareness, space constraints, and financial limitations continue to hinder widespread adoption. While compulsion remains the primary driver, voluntary uptake based on environmental awareness or self-interest is still limited.

Technical and economic considerations: RWH systems remain relatively affordable compared to alternative water sources, with many households historically spending below ₹15,000. However, inflation and deeper recharge designs now push costs to ₹20,000–70,000. Design deviations and poor maintenance, especially clogged filters, continue to erode system performance.

6. Conclusion

Rainwater harvesting and reuse systems have emerged as critical tools for addressing Bangalore's growing water scarcity. The city demonstrates two dominant RWH typologies: rooftop harvesting for non-potable uses and groundwater recharge systems, which collectively contribute to reducing reliance on tankers and overexploited borewells. Despite regulatory mandates, community awareness, and institutional support from BWSSB, KSCST, and BBMP, adoption remains uneven and largely compliance-driven. Technical challenges, maintenance issues, financial constraints, and spatial limitations continue to impede optimal performance. Nevertheless, survey and hydrogeological evidence confirm that RWH positively impacts groundwater levels and mitigates urban water stress. Scaling up adoption through a combination of incentives, technical guidance, public outreach, and community-driven initiatives can enhance water security, reduce dependence on external sources, and support sustainable urban development in Bangalore. Continued integration of policy, technology, and citizen participation

is essential to realize the full potential of RWH as a resilient, cost-effective, and environmentally sustainable water management strategy.

7. Future Directions

While the research has provided a comprehensive overview of the state of RWH in Bangalore, several areas warrant further exploration:

- **Data Gaps and Longitudinal Studies:** There is a lack of comprehensive data on the number of RWH installations across the city. Future research could focus on gathering data on the scale of implementation and performance metrics of RWH systems, particularly in less-urbanized or economically disadvantaged areas.
- **Primary Data Collection:** The current research relies heavily on secondary data. Future studies should incorporate primary data collection through field surveys and interviews with RWH system users to understand their challenges, experiences, and suggestions for improvement. This would offer more nuanced insights into the actual functioning of RWH systems in Bangalore.
- **Financial Models and Incentives:** Future research could explore innovative financial models to support the installation and maintenance of RWH systems. This could include exploring public-private partnerships, loan schemes, and other financial instruments to make RWH systems more affordable and accessible, particularly in low-income neighborhoods.
- **Enhancing Community Engagement & Governance:** Facilitate participatory planning with neighborhoods and institutions to shift from compulsion to intrinsic motivation, backed by public education campaigns and collaborative maintenance frameworks.

8. References

1. Ambika & Shankar. (2023). STUDY OF RAIN WATER HARVESTING IN BENGALURU URBAN REGIONS. *Journal of University of Shanghai for Science and Technology*.
2. Bosu, S. S. (1995). Sharing of Inter-state River Water Resources: Case Studies of Two Major Irrigation Systems in Tamil Nadu, India. *International Journal of Water Resources Development*, 11(4), 443–456. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07900629550042128>
3. B.PAC. (2024, March 22). *Droplets of Change: Addressing Bengaluru's Water Crisis with Sustainable Strategies*.
<https://bpac.in/bengaluru-water-crisis-causes-solutions/#:~:text=Improving%20Supply%3A&text=This%20includes%20watershed%20management%2C%20aquifer,solution%20to%20Bengaluru's%20water%20crisis>.
4. BWSSB. (2021, October 7). *Guidelines on Rain Water Harvesting: Amendments, Regulations and Guidelines*. Bangalore Water Supply and Sewerage Board (BWSSB).
[https://bwssb.karnataka.gov.in/storage/pdf-files/Rain%20Water%20Harvesting/Guidelines%20on%20Rain%20Water%20Harvesting%20\(1\).pdf](https://bwssb.karnataka.gov.in/storage/pdf-files/Rain%20Water%20Harvesting/Guidelines%20on%20Rain%20Water%20Harvesting%20(1).pdf)
5. Citizen Matters. (2025). *Rainwater Harvesting explained: What, why and how much*.
<https://citizenmatters.in/rainwater-harvesting-rwh-what-why-and-how-much-bengaluru/>
6. Garima, & Sridhar. (2025). Recharge plan: BBMP gears to catch more rain in pits. *Bangalore Mirror*.
<https://bangaloremirror.indiatimes.com/bangalore/civic/recharge-plan-bbmp-gears-to-catch-more-rain-in-pits/articleshow/117926926.cms>

7. Kulranjan, R., Palur, S., & Nesi, M. (2023). *How Water Flows Through Bengaluru: Urban Water Balance Report*.
8. Mehta, A., & Saroha, N. (2024, April 6). *Bengaluru's Water Crisis*.
<https://www.epw.in/journal/2024/14/letters/bengalurus-water-crisis.html>
9. Mint. (2024, March 18). *Bengaluru water crisis: CM Siddaramaiah says govt will provide water to all 110 villages near city in June*.
<https://www.livemint.com/news/india/bengaluru-water-crisis-siddaramaiah-says-his-govt-will-provide-water-to-110-villages-around-bengaluru-in-june-11710763167413.html>
10. Puran Choudhary. (2023, July 15). Rainwater harvesting in only 1.9 lakh buildings in Bengaluru. *The New Indian Express*.
<https://www.newindianexpress.com/cities/bengaluru/2023/Jul/15/rainwater-harvestingin-only19-lakh-buildings-in-bengaluru-2594896.html>
11. S. Vishwanath. (2015). *Domestic Rainwater Harvesting Some applications in Bangalore, India*.
<https://www.yumpu.com/en/document/view/33534174/domestic-rainwater-harvesting-some-applications-voiceofbharat>
12. SANDRP. (2025, March 5). *2024 Bengaluru Groundwater: Top ten Reports: Problems, Causes & Solutions*.
<https://sandrp.in/2025/03/05/2024-bengaluru-groundwater-top-ten-reports-problems-causes-solutions/>
13. Satpathy, S., & Jha, R. (2022). Intermittent water supply in Indian cities: Considering the intermittency beyond demand and supply. *Journal of Water Supply: Research and Technology-Aqua*, 71(12), 1395–1407. <https://doi.org/10.2166/aqua.2022.149>

14. The Hindu. (2024, March 18). *Bengaluru facing shortage of 500 MLD water daily, admits Chief Minister Siddaramaiah.*
<https://www.thehindu.com/news/cities/bangalore/bengaluru-facing-shortage-of-500-mld-water-daily-admits-chief-minister-siddaramaiah/article67964439.ece>
15. The New Indian Express. (2024). *Community RWH project to fill Bengaluru's lakes on the anvil.*
<https://www.newindianexpress.com/cities/bengaluru/2024/Mar/27/community-rwh-project-to-fill-bengalurus-lakes-on-the-anvil>
16. The Times of India. (2025, March 5). *Rainwater harvesting: Rs 2.7 crore penalty collected in January 2025 in Bengaluru.*
<https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/bengaluru/rainwater-harvesting-rs-2-7-crore-penalty-collected-in-january-2025-in-bengaluru/articleshow/118717272.cms>
17. Tomer, S. K., Sekhar, M., Balakrishnan, K., Malghan, D., Thiyaku, S., Gautam, M., & Mehta, V. K. (2021). A model-based estimate of the groundwater budget and associated uncertainties in Bengaluru, India. *Urban Water Journal*, 18(1), 1–11.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1573062X.2020.1836237>
18. Umamani, K. S., & Manasi, S. (2013). *RAINWATER HARVESTING INITIATIVE IN BANGALORE CITY: PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS.*
19. Vivek Kumar Sah. (2024, July 26). *Rainwater harvesting takes centre stage in Bengaluru's water crisis.*
<https://www.downtoearth.org.in/water/rainwater-harvesting-takes-centre-stage-in-bengaluru-water-crisis>
20. Raju KV, Ravindra A, Manasi S, et al. (2018) Trends and status of environmental resource use in Bangalore metropolitan area (BMA). In: Urban Environmental

Governance in India. The Urban Book Series. Cham: Springer. DOI:
10.1007/978-3-319-73468-2_6.